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Faculty of Medicine, University of Banja Luka, the Republic of Srpska, Bosnia & Herzegovina

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12-Oxocholedeoxycholic Acid Alleviates Doxorubicin-Induced Apoptosis of Cardiomyocytes *In Vivo*

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Abstract

Background/Aim: Secondary, latent effects of chemotherapy, including chronic cardiomyopathy, cast shadow on doxorubicin treatment in the modern era of oncology. The aim of this work is to assess the expression of apoptosis markers in heart tissue following doxorubicin administration in 12-oxocholedeoxycholic acid-pretreated animals.

Methods: 18 male Wistar rats were randomly assigned into 3 groups (n = 6). Saline was administered i.p. to control (C) group animals, whereas the doxorubicin was administered i.p. (3 mg/kg) for three days to doxorubicin (D) animals. The third experimental group, in addition to doxorubicin, was treated with a semisynthetic bile acid derivative, 12-oxocholedeoxycholic acid (26 mg/kg), by gastric gavage prior to doxorubicin administration for three days. 21 days after, animals were euthanized, hearts were harvested and parameters of apoptosis in heart tissue were assessed by RT-qPCR, relative to b-actin as a housekeeping gene. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA and Tuckey's post-hoc test.

Results: Doxorubicin treatment significantly increased expression of pro-apoptotic *Bax* compared to C (p < 0.001), whereas co-treatment with 12-oxocholedeoxycholic acid significantly reduced *Bax* expression (p < 0.001) compared to the D. The expression of an anti-apoptotic *Bcl-2* was significantly induced in both experimental groups, compared to C (p < 0.001). 12-oxocholedeoxycholic acid co-administration induced *Bcl-2* compared to D group (p < 0.001). *Bax/Bcl-2* ratio suggests that, in comparison to the control, doxorubicin has induced mitochondrial apoptotic pathway in cardiomyocytes (1.85 ± 0.89 vs. 9.44 ± 1.33, p = 0.001), as well as 12-oxocholedeoxycholic acid co-administration - but to a lesser extent (1.85 ± 0.89 vs. 6.29 ± 0.52, p = 0.024). Even though 12-oxocholedeoxycholic acid co-treatment reduced the *Bax/Bcl-2*, compared to doxorubicin-only treated animals, the reduction was not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Results of this *in vivo* study suggest that 12-oxocholedeoxycholic acid co-treatment with doxorubicin reduces apoptosis of cardiomyocytes 21 days following the finalization of treatment, showing promising potential in developing cardio-protective strategies, and in preventing delayed cardio-toxic effects.

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Key words: Apoptosis; Bile Acid; Cardio-oncology; Cardiomyopathy; Doxorubicin; Mitochondrial.

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